

tive stage to maturity. This means that grain yield for continuous shallow submergence can be achieved with 7-cm irrigation water applied 3 d after disappearance of ponded water, for a net savings of 24% of the water requirement (Table 2).

Applied N higher than 80 kg/ha did not significantly affect yield, and 40 kg N/ha appeared sufficient. The interaction of irrigation and N was not significant. □

Table 2. Effect of irrigation schedule and N level on water requirement and water-use efficiency of summer rice in Assam, India.

Treatment	Rainfall (mm)			Water requirement (mm)			Water-use efficiency (kg/ha/mm)			
	1987	1988	1989	1987	1988	1989	1987	1988	1989	Mean
Continuous submergence	504	1040	519	1304	1640	1149	1.71	0.83	2.30	1.61
7 cm water 1 DADPW	504	1040	519	1204	1390	1009	1.66	1.14	2.71	1.84
7 cm water 3 DADPW	504	1040	519	924	1320	869	2.23	1.23	3.26	2.24

Improving applied phosphorus utilization by rice in Madagascar

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On the Fe-toxic, low-P soils of the Central Highlands of Madagascar, broadcast P fertilizers are fixed by the Fe and poorly utilized by the rice plant. Resource-poor farmers often cannot afford to apply the recommended 26 kg P/ha.

We compared applying 13 kg P/ha (1/2 the recommended rate) by broadcast and incorporation and by seedling root dipping, in a farmer's field in Manjakandriana (1,420 m) for 4 yr. Soil was 49% clay, 21% silt, 30% sand, pH 4.9, and had 3.31% organic C, CEC 10.2 meq, 5.3 ppm available P.

Effect of P rate and method of application on yield of Chianan 8, transplanted on an Fe-toxic soil, Sambaina, Manjakandriana, Madagascar.

Treatment ^a	Yield ^b (t/ha)				
	1985/86	1986/87	1987/88	1988/89	Mean
No fertilizer	2.5 d	0.8 c	0.9 c	1.1 d	1.4
NK only	3.7 c	0.8 c	1.1 c	1.6 c	1.8
NK + 13 kg/ha B/I	3.9 bc	1.3 b	2.3 b	2.2 b	2.4
NK + 13 kg P/ha root dipping	4.2 ab	2.0 a	3.0 a	2.6 a	3.0
NK + 26 kg P/ha B/I	4.4 a	1.4 b	2.4 b	2.2 b	2.6

^a B/I = broadcast and incorporated. N = 60 and K = 50 kg/ha. ^b In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Triple superphosphate (TSP) was dissolved in water and soil was added until a sticky paste was formed (approximately 1:4:6 of TSP, water, and soil). Seedling roots were coated in the paste and immediately transplanted. (The first year, rice roots were dipped in a mixture of water and TSP.) N and K were applied at 60 and 50 kg/ha, respectively.

Averaged over 4 yr, root dipping was 22% more effective than broadcasting

and incorporating TSP, and root dipping with 13 kg P/ha was as effective as broadcasting and incorporating 26 kg P/ha (see table). Leaf tissue analysis showed higher P levels in plants fertilized by seedling root dipping.

Concentrating the P around the roots probably reduces the amount of P fixed by the soil and makes more P immediately available to the rice plant. □

Integrated pest management—diseases

Association of *Fusarium moniliforme* Sheld. with rice seeds and subsequent infection in Pakistan

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Rice bakanae disease caused by *Fusarium moniliforme* Sheld.—perfect stage *Gibberella fujikuroi* Sawada—is becoming a serious threat to rice production in Pakistan. We collected rice seed

samples from nine localities to assess its incidence.

Seeds treated with 0.1% mercuric chloride for 1 min and untreated seeds, 400/sample, were studied. Twenty seeds per sterilized petri plate were plated on three layers of moistened blotter paper and kept at 25 °C in 12 h light, 12 h dark for 7 d. These seeds were examined under a stereoscope; microscopic slides also were studied for identification.

Other seeds from the same samples were grown separately in sterilized pots, and isolations from the vascular system

of the seedlings were made on Richard's agar medium at 27 °C. A third set of seeds was planted and typical bakanae disease symptoms on the mature plants measured.

Seeds from all localities but D. G. Khan showed the presence of *F. moniliforme*. Maximum presence of fungus on seeds was 19.75%. Nearly 20% of the seeds treated with 0.1% mercuric chloride from Gujranwala showed presence of the fungus (see table).

When the seeds were not treated before plating, highest fungus infection was near 12% in those from Sialkot. In most cases, fungus intensity was higher